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Progress report on strategies adopted to align HBM studies across Europe and preliminary results

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D8.8

WP8 - Targeted field work surveys and alignment at EU level

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Glossary

BEA = Biomonitorización en Adolescentes

BFRs = Brominated Flame retardants

BPA = Bisphenol A

BPF= Bisphenol F

BPS = Bisphenol S

(C)ELSPAC = European Longitudinal Study of Pregnancy and Childhood

CPHMINIPUB parents = Copenhagen Minipuberty study (parents)

CROME = Cross-Mediterranean Environment and Health Network

DEMOCOPHES = DEMONstration of a study to COordinate and Perform Human Biomonitoring on a European Scale

DIET_HBM = Icelandic National Dietary Survey 2019 - Human Biomonitoring Substudy

EQUAS = External Quality Assurance scheme

ESB = Environmental Specimen Bank

ESTEBAN = Étude de santé sur l'environnement, la biosurveillance, l'activité physique et la nutrition

FLEHS IV = Flemish Environment and Health study IV

GDPR = General Data Protection Regulation

GerES V = German Environmental Surveys V

HBM = Human Biomonitoring

ICI = Interlaboratory Comparison Investigations

InAirQ = Indoor Air Quality

INSEF-ExQAP = Exposure of the Portuguese Population to Environmental Chemicals: a study nested in INSEF 2015

IPCHEM = Information Platform for Chemical Monitoring data

LOQ = limit of quantification

NAC II = Northern Adriatic cohort II

NEB II = Norwegian Environmental Biobank II

OCC = Odense child cohort

OPFRs = Organophosphate flame retardants

PAHs = Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

PCB cohort = Endocrine disruptors in children and associated health effects

PFAS = per-/poly-fluorinated compounds

SLO CRP = Exposure of children and adolescents to selected chemicals through their habitat environment

SOP's = Standard operating procedures

SAP = Statistical analysis plan

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Abstract

The aim of task 8.1 is to align ongoing/planned studies to collect HBM data of the prioritised chemicals with EU wide coverage. To realise this task a European sampling frame was developed. We started from a theoretical concept describing criteria related to recruitment and sampling to obtain current exposure data across Europe. Current exposure was hereby defined as samples taken between 2014 and 2019 i.e. over the last 5 years. This concept was then adapted to fit reality. The 3 age groups of focus are: children (6-11 yrs), teenagers (12-19 yrs) and adults (20-39 yrs). Within each age group specific chemicals are addressed. For children phthalates/DINCH and flame retardants will be analysed, for teenagers phthalates/DINCH and per-/poly- fluorinated compounds will be analysed and in adults cadmium, bisphenols and Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons (PAHs) exposure will be analysed. 21 different countries, representing north, east, south and west Europe participate in the sampling frame. This will result in chemical exposure data of 2950 children, 2900 teenagers and 3165 adults distributed across Europe. This will be an exciting first step towards a first EU wide HBM survey.

The alignment of studies is ongoing, sample collection has been finalised for most studies. The analytical phase is initiated and harmonisation of the questionnaire data is ongoing. Data are expected by M40.

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Introduction

To realise task 8.1 we have established a sampling frame for Europe as explained in D8.1. Based on the inventory resulting from the WP7.1 questionnaire, data gaps for the first set of priority chemicals were identified. Subsequently, national hubs and Principal Investigators (PI) from potentially eligible studies were invited for bilateral telephone conferences to discuss opportunities for participation in the alignment of studies and potential hurdles. As a result of these discussions, we realised that adaptations to the theoretical sampling frame were needed to fit reality. These adaptations are detailed in [D8.1 "Description of the national programs A strategy to collect EU wide HBM data"](#).

The resulting approach has been presented to the governing board, the advisory board, the stakeholder forum and several times at meetings of the management board. All studies that fit the sampling frame and that agreed with the conditions to participate were accepted to participate in the alignment of studies. This resulted in 33 studies from 21 different European countries that together will contribute to the first EU wide HBM survey. An overview of the contributing studies is detailed in [D8.4 "Initial report on strategies adopted to align studies across Europe"](#).

The present deliverable (D8.8) reports the progress of the studies, the study characteristics are compared and the challenges faced in this alignment/harmonisation process are discussed.

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1 Progress of alignment of studies

1.1 Sample collection

Nine studies that focus on **children** (NEB II, OCC, PCB cohort, InAirQ, POLAES, SLO CRP, NAC II, GerES V, ESTEBAN) have finalised sample collection. Sample collection for CROME is ongoing and planned to be finalised December 2019. Sample collection for Youth cohort has not been initiated yet¹. Earliest opportunity for sample collection is March 2020.

Eight studies that focus on **teenagers** (NEB II, Riksmaten, POLAES, SLO CRP, BEA, ESTEBAN, FLEHS IV, GerES V) have finalised sample collection. Sample collection for Pilot study in school children in Czech Republic, CROME and PCB follow-up, is ongoing and was planned to be finalised December 2019.

Nine studies that focus on **adults** (CPHMINIPUB parents, FinHealth, (C)ELSPAC, Oriscav-Lux2, POLAES, ESB, ESTEBAN, INSEF-ExQAP, HBM in adults in Croatia) have finalised their sample collection. Sample collection for DIET-HBM is ongoing and planned to be finalised March 2020, sample collection for SWISS TPH is ongoing and planned to be finalised September 2020.

1.2 Sample analysis

The results of 2nd ICI/EQUAS round of the HBM4EU QA/QC programme have been made available in July 2019. The list of qualified labs per parameter was updated in October 2019 after the finalisation of the 3rd round. Since then the analytical phase has been initiated. The aligned studies are selecting the laboratories for analysis and the first samples have been transported and analysis has been initiated. The analytical phase is being tracked by T9.5 and more details are available in [AD9.3 "Report on activities in the analytical phase"](#).

¹ This delay is due to a change in the management board of the Youth cohort which has put activities on hold.

2 How homo-/heterogeneous are the studies to be aligned?

Despite the inclusion criteria which were defined for participation in the sampling frame how homogeneous are the studies to be aligned? In this section we compare and discuss the following characteristics of the studies to be aligned: level of representativeness, time frame, age distribution, sample type and seasonal coverage of sampling campaigns.

2.1 Representativeness

In the original task description of WP 8 it was defined that **National representative studies** should be aligned to derive current internal exposure data representative for the European population/citizens. However, we also needed to build on existing capacity. Once we started to contact available studies in Europe we found out that it would not be possible to build on national representative studies only therefore, it was decided to also include regional studies (see [D8.1](#), [D8.4](#)).

In the aligned studies of children there are 4 national representative² studies (NO, FR, DE, HU) and 7 regionally representative studies (DK, SK, PL, SI, EL, IT, NL). In the aligned studies of teenagers there are 5 nationally representative² studies (NO, SE, FR, DE, ES) and 6 regionally representative studies (SK, PL, SI, EL, BE, CZ). In the aligned studies of adults there are 6 studies which are representative on national² level (IS, FI, PT, HR, FR, LU) and 5 studies which are only representative for a specific region and thus not for the entire country. (DK, PL, CH, DE, CZ).

Hence for all age groups some national representative² HBM surveys were included across Europe, but most countries participating in the alignment have HBM surveys implemented at regional level (see Figure 1).

All the studies are contributing with a maximum of 300 samples. Since some studies have more than 300 samples available they were asked to make a selection of 300 samples out of their total sample size. Guidelines on how to make this selection that is as representative as possible of the target population were provided by WP10 (see appendix).

Figure 1: Level of representativeness of aligned studies in children, teenagers and adults

² The **original** studies are national representative but not necessarily the 300 selected samples.

2.2 Building on existing capacity

Another important aspect of building a European HBM platform is that we build on existing capacity. Doing so means that we are dealing with studies which use biobanked samples, studies that collect new samples within the frame of HBM4EU and studies that collect new samples using HBM4EU protocols. Only those studies who started their fieldwork campaign second half of 2018 were able to align their protocols with the HBM4EU developed protocols.

In the aligned studies of children there are 6 studies contributing with biobanked samples (NO, DK, SK, IT, FR, DE), 3 studies that collected samples during HBM4EU (HU, PL, SI) and 2 studies that collect new samples following HBM4EU protocols (NL, EL). In the aligned studies of teenagers there are 4 studies contributing with biobanked samples (NO, SE, FR, DE), 4 studies that collected samples during HBM4EU (PL, SI, ES, BE) and 3 studies that collect new samples following HBM4EU protocols (CZ, EL, SK). In the aligned studies of adults there are 3 studies contributing with biobanked samples (LU, DE, FR), 3 studies that collected samples during HBM4EU (PL, FI, DK) and 5 studies that collect new samples following HBM4EU protocols (CH, HR, PT, CZ, IS).

Figure 2: Aligned studies are building on (ongoing) HBM initiatives in Europe

³ Biobanked samples = samples collected before HBM4EU (before 2017).

⁴ New sample collection during HBM4EU = samples collected between 2017-2020 but the planning phase of the study was already concluded and protocols and questionnaires could not be aligned with HBM4EU SO'P's and questionnaires.

2.3 Time frame

We defined inclusion criteria for studies to be eligible to participate in the alignment of studies. One of the criteria was the time period of sampling that we defined. Samples needed to be collected between 2014-2019 i.e. last 5 years to reflect “recent exposure”. In Figure 3 the time frames covered by the aligned studies of children, teenagers and adults are presented. The exact time periods covered vary between the individual studies. In the studies targeting children there is one study (Youth cohort, NL⁵) that is delayed and will fall outside the timeframe defined. Also in the studies targeting adults, there are two studies (SWISS TPH, CH; DIET_HBM, IS) that will fall outside the timeframe defined.

Figure 3: Time frame of aligned studies in children, teenagers and adults

⁵ This delay is due to a change in the management board of the Youth cohort which has put activities on hold.

2.4 Age distribution

Besides the time frame we also defined the age groups of interest. Children age 6-11, teenagers age 12-19 and adults age 20-39. Figure 4 shows the age distribution of the children's studies to be aligned. Some of the studies like ESTEBAN, Norwegian Environmental Biobank II (NEB II) cover the entire age range (6-11 years). Whereas some other studies target only 7-year-old children like the Odense child cohort (OCC) and the Northern Adriatic cohort from Italy (NAC II). Although the age range is aligned, the exact ages covered by the studies varies. As a result, some ages are stronger represented in the overall study population group. The same holds for the other age groups.

Figure 4: Age distribution of aligned studies in children, teenagers and adults

2.5 Sample types

Different types of urine samples can be collected. 24-hour samples, random spot samples or first morning spot samples. In the HBM4EU developed SOP's, collection of first morning urine samples is recommended as they are less diluted which maximises the chance for the target biomarker to be above the limit of quantification (LOQ).

In the aligned studies of children, 5 out of 11 studies collected first morning void, 6 out of 11 studies collected random spot samples (see Table 5). In the aligned studies targeting teenagers, 7 out of 11 studies collected first morning void, 4 out of /11 studies collected random spot samples (see Table 6). In the aligned studies of adults, 5 out of 11 studies collected first morning void, 5 out of 11 studies collected random spot samples and one study collected 24-hour urine samples (see Table 7). Although 24-hour samples represent the excreted fraction over the entire day, usually spot urine samples are collected instead of 24-hour samples as the latter are more inconvenient to collect and are more likely to become contaminated due to continuous opening of the vessel.

These differences in sample collection procedures should be considered in the statistical analysis.

2.6 Seasonality

Another aspect is seasonal coverage. Preferably, the sample collection campaign covers all 4 seasons to capture seasonal variation in exposure. Having coverage of all 4 seasons is especially important for those exposures which have seasonal variation. An example is the exposure to PAHs which will be assessed in the aligned studies of adults. Only 4 out of 11 studies have samples collected across all 4 seasons. In studies of children 7 out of 11 studies have collected samples over all 4 seasons (see appendix, Table 5) and in studies of teenagers 5 out of 11 studies have collected samples over all 4 seasons (see appendix, Table 6). Table 1 provides an overview of the seasonal coverage of aligned studies in adults.

Table 1: Seasonal coverage of aligned studies of adults

Country	Study	Spring 			
Denmark	CPMINIPUB (parents)	√	√	√	√
Iceland	DIET_HBM	-	-	√	√
Finland	FinHealth	√	-	-	√
Poland	POLAES	-	-	√	√
Czech Republic	ELSPAC	√	√	√	-
Croatia	HBM in adults in Croatia	√	-	-	√
Portugal	INSEF-ExQAP	√	-	-	√
France	ESTEBAN	√	√	√	√
Switzerland	SWISS TPH	√	√	√	√
Germany	ESB	√	-	-	√
Luxembourg	Oriscav	√	√	√	√

As discussed in the sections above there are still differences between the studies in terms of study design, age and time period covered, sample types collected, seasonal coverage etc.

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Most of the differences are situated in the early phases of study conduct i.e. in the recruitment and sample collection phase. We achieve a higher degree of harmonisation in the later stages of study conduct. Since the transport of the samples to the laboratories all follow the HBM4EU standard operating procedures, the chemical analysis needs to be performed in HBM4EU quality approved laboratories, the data will be harmonised following the HBM4EU codebook and will be combined in the central database at VITO. The statistical analysis will be performed at EU level following the SAP developed in WP10.

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3 Challenges

Given the requirement of the HBM4EU project to build on existing capacity it was not feasible to initiate new HBM studies as was done in the DEMOCOPHES project. As a consequence, within the joint HBM survey, ongoing European HBM initiatives are aligned and harmonised to achieve internal exposure data of priority chemicals in the European population. The HBM4EU project and in particular the joint HBM survey provides a platform to exchange best practices and improve and align HBM conduct in Europe.

A harmonised and coordinated European approach is currently lacking. There are several good examples of national representative HBM programs in Europe but they are aimed at national interests in terms of (sub-)populations included and measured biomarkers. No overarching strategy exists and studies are not harmonised and aligned to common goals. Aligning (ongoing) HBM surveys across Europe poses several challenges that need to be overcome to improve the comparability of internal exposure data of European citizens.

3.1 Post-harmonisation of questionnaire data

A first challenge encountered in aligning HBM surveys across Europe is the post-harmonisation of questionnaire data. All participating studies collected basic individual information on socio-demographics and information on environmental- and lifestyle-related exposure through questionnaires. The method applied to conduct the questionnaires differed between the individual studies. In the alignment of studies task 8.1 both ongoing studies, that collect new samples, as well as recently conducted studies, that provide biobanked samples are included. New studies or ongoing studies that were still in the planning phase and could adapt their questionnaires were asked to align their questionnaire with the questionnaire developed within the frame of HBM4EU. In the case of biobanked samples, the questionnaires of those studies were already developed and conducted. Thus, they could not be aligned upfront. Therefore, a post-harmonisation approach is required to harmonise the questionnaire data across studies.

A step-wise approach has been developed relying on collaboration between partners from WP7, WP8 and WP10. **As a first step** partners of task 7.3, who developed the substance specific questionnaires for the first set of priority substances, and partners of task 10.4, who developed the statistical analysis protocols, were consulted to provide a list of information items (variables) relevant for calculating reference values, geographical comparisons, time trend analysis and/or analysis of exposure determinants (personal, life style or environmental characteristics that may influence internal exposure levels). These variables were specific for the substances and age groups under study i.e. phthalates, DINCH and flame retardants in children, phthalates, DINCH and PFAS in teenagers and bisphenols, PAH and cadmium in adults. Based on their input a comprehensive list of variables was compiled highlighting all important information items per chemical and age group. In a **second step** the aligned studies have to cross check their own questionnaires with this list and indicate which information they have available. In case they have the information available they have to provide an English translation of the related question and the accompanying answer options (in case of multiple-choice questions) or unit.

In a third step all the information from the aligned studies is combined and compared. Study specific variables are converted to harmonised variables. This process involved summarising, checking and matching the specific variable study-by-study and deciding on a common coding system appropriate to each variable (WP10).

Once the codebook is developed by WP10, the aligned studies need to transform their questionnaire data into harmonised variables according to the codebook. The aligned studies will

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be supported in this transformation process by partners from WP 10. This step-wise approach is illustrated in figure 1.

All the studies will report their individual data in a similar way using the harmonised codebook which is already developed centrally on EU level. This post-harmonisation approach is very time consuming and has its limitations. Basic variables such as age, gender, smoking behavior etc. can be harmonised across all studies. More specific information such as i.e. consumption of canned food cannot be harmonised for all studies since the information is not available in all studies.

This post-harmonisation process showed that there is currently, quite some variation in the questionnaires used in HBM surveys in Europe. Especially harmonising food frequency questions and questions related to frequency of product use are proven difficult to harmonise since the window of exposure addressed in the different questionnaires are not aligned. Some questionnaires ask frequency over the last 12 months, some over the last 4 weeks, others over the last 3 months or in the last days prior to sample collection.

Step 3 has recently been finalised and the aligned studies can now initiate step 4 to harmonise their questionnaire data. Deadline for providing the questionnaire data in harmonised format is M36.

Post-harmonisation strategy

Figure 5: Step-wise post-harmonisation approach for harmonising questionnaire data from aligned studies.

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3.2 Harmonising exposure biomarkers across studies

A second challenge encountered in aligning HBM surveys across Europe is to harmonise the chemical biomarkers which will be analysed in the studies. An important aspect of HBM4EU is capacity building, making full use of the expertise and experience available within the individual countries and sharing this expertise and experience with one another. On the other hand, we also want to be very ambitious and want to generate new results not only for the well-known markers but also for novel exposure markers.

To guarantee that the same exposure biomarkers are analysed in the studies WP9 defined scenarios (i.e. a combination of exposure biomarkers) for each substance group which should be analysed by the aligned studies, considering analytical issues and exposure interest among others. This resulted in scenario 1 (the minimal scenario's), scenario 2 (scenario's recommended by policy board) and scenario 3 (extended scenario's) (see Table 2). However, after the results of the 2nd ICI/EQUAS round it became clear that it is not possible to adhere to these scenario's because a limited number of laboratories obtained successful results for those specific combinations of biomarkers as defined in the scenarios. This partially due to the fact that at the beginning of the ICI/EQUAS a minimum mandatory participation was not defined and candidate laboratories decided themselves for which exposure biomarkers they would participate in the ICI/EQUAS scheme. This illustrates that there are still efforts needed to improve analytical capacity in Europe to guarantee comparable exposure data of a minimal set of biomarkers. The aligned studies are encouraged to analyse as many biomarkers as possible. For cadmium and DINCH (OH-MINCH, cx-MINCH) a minimal coverage will be achieved in all aligned studies.

Table 2: Case example: Exposure to bisphenols in adults

Case example: Exposure to bisphenols in adults					
<p>BPA is the most used and best known chemical of the bisphenol substance group. However, BPA substitutes like BPS and BPF are increasingly used. Recently the use of BPA in thermal papers was restricted under REACH. This might orchestrate a shift from BPA to these BPA substitutes. Currently, there are not many Human Biomonitoring studies that analysed BPS and BPF. Therefore, it would be beneficial to have data on BPS and BPF exposures prior to 2020 to be able to monitor a potential shift from BPA to BPA substitutes (BPS/BPF) exposure to allow an evaluation of the impact of this policy measure.</p> <p>However, taking a look at the capacity of the European laboratories qualified selected by the aligned studies to perform the analysis of bisphenols it becomes clear that not all of the qualified laboratories are able to generate comparable data for BPA, BPS and BPF. Out of the 24 laboratories that have qualified for Bisphenols only 6 are qualified for all 3 bisphenols (BPA, BPS and BPF).</p>					
Minimal scenario		BPA			
Recommended scenario		BPA + BPS			
Extended scenario		BPA + BPS + BPF			
	Name study	country	BPA	BPS	BPF
North	CPHMINIPUB (parents)	Denmark			
	Diet_HBM	Iceland			
	FinHealth	Finland			
East	POLAES	Poland			
	CELSPAC	Czech Republic			
South	HBM in adults	Croatia			
	INSEF-ExQAP	Portugal			
West	ESTEBAN	France			
	SWISS TPH	Switzerland			
	Oriscav Lux 2	Luxembourg			
	Analysis confirmed		Will not be analysed		
<p>Finding a balance between capacity building on one hand and the HBM4EU-projects ambition on the other hand means we need to compromise.</p>					

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3.3 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

A third challenge we face is the GDPR. Since the GDPR came into force May 2018 we needed to make sure that the data are handled and exchanged in a GDPR compliant way. At the beginning of the HBM4EU project it was defined that (pseudonymised) individual HBM data would be exchanged using the HBM4EU repository which is part of the IPCHEM architecture. However, at this point IPCHEM cannot facilitate the exchange of this type of sensitive data. Therefore, an alternative has been worked out to facilitate the exchange of individual data from the aligned studies. The individual data from the aligned studies will be hosted at VITO in a central database and pooled into 3 European datasets. 1 dataset for children, 1 dataset for teenagers and 1 dataset for adults.

The structure of the database is designed to guarantee GDPR compliance. The process is supervised by the VITO DPO. VITO will act as a data processor in hosting the data.

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4 Plans for 2020-2021

4.1 Implementation of second set priority chemicals

In November 2018 a first inquiry was sent out to the aligned study partners to provide a first non-binding interest indication on implementing analysis of second set priority chemicals in the aligned studies. In a second stage also the national hubs were consulted. Based on the interests, following proposals for analysis were considered as most feasible to implement:

- ✓ Pesticides in children (glyphosate, AMPA, pyrethroids, chlorpyrifos)
- ✓ Arsenic species in teenagers
- ✓ Mycotoxins in adults
- ✓ UV-filters in adults (first choice)
- ✓ UV-filters in teenagers (second choice)
- ✓ Acrylamide in adults and children

Criteria for implementing biomarker analysis for the second set priority chemicals in aligned studies are:

- ✓ Need to include at least 1 country per EU region
- ✓ Chemical analysis is 50% co-funded
- ✓ Chemical analysis should be performed in an expert lab qualified by WP9
- ✓ A fixed set of biomarkers needs to be analysed in all participating countries (see list of selected biomarkers in Table 4)

The final overview of aligned studies that will implement analysis of second set priority chemicals will be detailed in AD8.3.

4.2 Implementation of biomarkers of effect as proof-of-principle

One of the objectives of HBM4EU is to generate scientific evidence on the causal relationships between exposure to prioritised chemical stressors and adverse health effects with public health implications. To this end, biomarkers of exposure are complemented with biomarkers of effect, which are measurable molecular, cellular, biochemical, physiologic, behavioural, structural or other alterations in an organism occurring along the temporal and mechanistic pathways connecting exposure to chemicals and an established or possible health impairment or disease.

We propose to implement novel molecular and some more traditional clinical effect biomarkers in the HBM4EU aligned studies organised in WP8, as a **proof of principle** to test the hypothesis that implementation of specific effect biomarkers may enhance the interpretation of exposure biomarker measurements and increase the weight of evidence of exposure-health outcome associations in human observational studies. Although most aligned studies have a cross sectional study design and hence are not well suited for studying the association of the exposures with final health outcomes that may develop only later in time, **our aim is to associate the measured exposures with early molecular changes that may be considered as the biological imprint of the exposure.**

We hypothesise that studying the associations between exposure biomarkers and effect biomarkers with the possibility to combine with health endpoints will enhance knowledge on the

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biological impact of chemical exposure, thereby providing insight into mechanisms of action and/or serving as a first step in the confirmation of hypotheses on exposure-health outcome associations.

The proposal is under development and covers:

- Neurodevelopment in children
- Metabolism and BMI in teenagers
- Sexual maturation in teenagers

The final overview of aligned studies that will implement analysis of effect biomarkers will be detailed in AD8.3.

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5 Appendix

5.1 Statistical working group WP10

Note concerning the selection of 300 samples in task 8.1

Constituted by the following partners:

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In the T8.1 aligned studies, chemical analyses are planned in 300 biological samples per study. As some of the data collections include more than 300 participants, a subset of 300 participants should be selected that is as representative as possible of the target population. At the statistical working group meeting (21st-22nd March 2019), WP10 partners have discussed a strategy for selection.

A stepwise approach is suggested for the selection of 300 participants.

In a first step, the following criteria should hold for the 300 participants to be included in each data collection: only participants should be included that lived at least 5 years in the catchment area and the participants should not be hospitalized/institutionalized.

All available data collections of the teenager sampling frame of T8.1 have study participants between 12 years of age up to 17 years of age, except ESTEBAN (France) that has recruited participants until 19 years of age. As such it was decided to include only participants of 12, 13, 14, 15, 16 and 17 years of age and to exclude participants of 18 and 19 years old.

In a second step, case subjects should be selected from the remaining participants, according to the following criteria:

- Appropriate sampling matrix (for example for teenagers: blood for PFASs and urine for phthalate/DINCH measurements)
- Appropriate sample volume available (sampling volume to be agreed upon with analytical laboratory, for more information contact Katrin Vorkamp: kvo@envs.au.dk), samples stored under appropriate conditions
- Necessary questionnaire and sample information available (not missing), i.e. the variables listed in the basic codebook of HBM4EU (basic codebook can be found in data management zip folder on the [internal](#) webpages, for more information contact HBM4EU.DATAMANAGEMENT@vito.be)

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In a third step, stratification of the participants into mutually exclusive subgroups should be applied and proportions should be defined. The following stratifications should be performed in chronological order:

- Sex of the participant: equal number of males and females, i.e. 50% \pm 2% of each sex should be represented.
- Degree of urbanization: at least 10% of each of the three levels should be represented. For this the variable degree of urbanization should be determined for each data collection according to Eurostat categorization into densely populated areas (cities), intermediate density areas (towns or suburbs) and thinly populated areas (rural area). To calculate the degree of urbanization of each participant in your data collection, please contact the data management team (HBM4EU.DATAMANAGEMENT@vito.be) for the specific information and files needed.
- Educational level: at least 10% of each of the three levels should be represented. This variable is based on the ISCED 2011 with 9 levels of education, being categorized into low (ISCED 0-2), medium (ISCED 3-4) and high (ISCED 5-8) educational level. For the studies of the children and teenagers sampling frame, the highest educational level of the household is preferred if available. If not available, the educational level of the mother should be used. For more information or assistance in the ISCED classification, please contact the data management team (HBM4EU.DATAMANAGEMENT@vito.be).
- Sampling season: more or less equal distribution over all seasons, i.e. 25% \pm 5% of each season.
- Age: cross-check in the end if all ages available in the original data collection are covered in the subset of 300 participants.

If for a certain stratifying variable, only one level is available in the original data collection (e.g. only participants from cities were recruited), this stratifying parameter should be discarded in the stratification process. If for a certain stratifying variable less levels are available (e.g. participants in the original data collections were not recruited during summer), then this level of the stratifying variable should be ignored in the stratification (e.g. more or less equal distribution of the remaining seasons should be represented).

As a final step, random selection of the participants adhering to the subgroup population proportions.

This is off course the ideal scenario and will probably not be reached by all studies. As the situation could differ between data collections, individual support and advice could be given to each data collection separately by the data management team and/or statistical working group, please contact HBM4EU.DATAMANAGEMENT@vito.be.

Table 3: Proposed scenarios for phthalates, DINCH, OPFRs, Cd, bisphenols and PAHs in urine, PFAS, and BFRs in serum

Substance group	Parameter	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
PHTHALATES	MEP	-	X	X
	MBzP	X	X	X
	MiBP	X	X	X
	MnBP	X	X	X
	MCHP	-	-	X
	MnPeP	-	-	-
	MEHP	X	X	X
	5OH-MEHP	X	X	X
	5oxo-MEHP	X	X	X
	5cx-MEPP	X	X	X
	MnOP	-	-	X
	OH-MiNP	-	X	X
	cx-MiNP	-	X	X
	OH-MiDP	-	X	X
cx-MiDP	-	X	X	
DINCH	OH-MINCH	X	-	-
	cx-MINCH	X	-	-
PFAS	PFPeA	-	X	-
	PFHxA	X	X	-
	PFHpA	-	X	-
	PFOA	X	X	-
	PFNA	X	X	-
	PFDA	-	X	-
	PFUnDA	-	X	-
	PFDoDA	-	X	-
	PFBS	X	X	-
	PFHxS	X	X	-
	PFHpS	-	X	-
	PFOS	X	X	-
BFRs	BDE-47	X	X	X
	BDE-153	X	X	X
	BDE-209	X	X	X
	α -HBCD	-	X	X
	γ -HBCD	-	X	X
	TBBPA	-	-	-
	Syn-DP	-	-	X
	Anti-DP	-	-	X
	DBDPE	-	-	-
2,4,6-Tribromophenol	-	-	-	

Substance group	Parameter	Scenario 1	Scenario 2	Scenario 3
OPFRs	<i>Not possible the definition of scenarios, due to a too small number of participants the 1st ICI and a too small number of expert laboratories in the 1st EQUAS.</i>			
Cadmium	Cd in urine	X	-	-
BISPHENOLS	BPA	X	X	X
	BPF	-	-	X
	BPS	-	X	X
PAHs	1-hydroxynaphthalene	X	X	X
	2-hydroxynaphthalene	X	X	X
	1,2-dihydroxynaphthalene	-	-	-
	2-hydroxyfluorene	-	-	X
	3-hydroxyfluorene	-	-	X
	9-hydroxyfluorene	-	-	X
	1-hydroxyphenanthrene	-	X	X
	2-hydroxyphenanthrene	-	X	X
	3-hydroxyphenanthrene	-	X	X
	4-hydroxyphenanthrene	-	X	X
	9-hydroxyphenanthrene	-	-	X
	1-hydroxypyrene	X	X	X
3-hydroxybenzo(a)pyrene	-	-	-	

Table 4: List of biomarkers of second set priority chemicals selected for implementation in aligned studies.

Substance	Parameters	Matrix (amount)	Analytical method	MDL
Arsenic	Arsenic (total)	urine (0.2 mL)	ICP-MS, AAS	< 0.05 ng/mL
	As (III)	urine (0.2-1 mL)	HPLC-ICP-MS	< 0.05 ng/mL
	As (V)	urine (0.2-1 mL)	HPLC-ICP-MS	< 0.05 ng/mL
	Monomethylarsonic acid (MMA)	urine (0.2-1 mL)	HPLC-ICP-MS	< 0.05 ng/mL
	Dimethylarsinic acid (DMA)	urine (0.2-1 mL)	HPLC-ICP-MS	< 0.05 ng/mL
	Arsenobetaine	urine		
Pesticides	3,5,6-trichloro-2-pyridinol (TCPy)	Urine (1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.1-0.5 ng/mL
	Glyphosate	Urine (0.1-0.5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.02-0.5 ng/mL
	Aminomethylphosphonic acid (AMPA)			
	cis-(2,2-dibromovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid (cis-DBCA)	Urine (1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.01-0.4 ng/mL
	cis-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (cis-DCCA)	Urine (1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.01-0.4 ng/mL
	trans-3-(2,2-dichlorovinyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropane-1-carboxylic acid (trans-DCCA)	Urine (1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.01-0.4 ng/mL
	3-PBA	Urine (1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.01-0.1 ng/mL
	4-fluoro-3-phenoxybenzoic acid (4-F-3-PBA)	Urine (1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.01-0.2 ng/mL
	cis-3-(2-chloro-3,3,3-trifluoroprop-1-enyl)-2,2-dimethylcyclopropanecarboxylic acid (CIF3CA)	Urine 5mL	GC-MS/MS	0.01 ng/mL
UV-filters	2,4-Dihydroxybenzophenone (BP1)	Urine (0.1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.03-0.5 ng/mL
	2,2',4,4'-Tetrahydroxybenzophenone (BP2)	Urine (0.1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.02-0.4 ng/mL
	2-Hydroxy-4-methoxybenzophenone (BP3)	Urine (0.1-5 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.06-0.5 ng/mL
	5-Chloro-2-hydroxybenzophenone (BP7)	Urine (0.1 mL)	LC-MS/MS	0.4 ng/mL
Mycotoxins	Deoxynivalenol (total)	Urine 0.5-2 mL	LC-MS/MS	≤ 0.3 ng/mL

Table 5: Comparison of study characteristics of studies to be aligned targeting children.

Children											
	North		East			South			West		
	NEBII	OCC	InAir Q	PCB cohort	POLAES	SLO CRP	CROME	NAC II	ESTEBAN	GerES V	YOUTH cohort
<i>Study characteristics</i>											
N	300	300	264	300	300	148	150	300	300	300	300
Age (years)	6-11	7	9-11	10-11	7-11	6-9	6-12	7	6-11	6-11	8-10
years of sample collection	2016	2017-2018	2017-2018	2014-2017	2017	2018	2019	2014-2016	2014-2016	2014-2016	2020
Seasonality											
Spring	√	√	√	√	-	√	-	√	√	√	√
Summer	√	√	-	√	-	√	-	√	√	√	√
Autumn	√	√	√	√	√	-	√	√	√	√	√
winter	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Representation	National	Regional	National	Regional	Regional	Regional	Regional	Regional	National	National	Regional
Study design	Longitudinal	Longitudinal	Cross-sectional	Longitudinal	Case-control	Cross-sectional	Cross-sectional	Longitudinal	Cross-sectional	Cross-sectional	Longitudinal
<i>Fieldwork methods / samples collected</i>											
Field blanks collected	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fasting status	Non-fasting	Fasting	-	-	-	Non-fasting	Fasting	-	Fasting	Non-fasting	-
Type urine sample	First morning void	Spot (random)	Spot (random)	Spot (random)	Spot (random)-	First morning void	First morning void	Spot (random)	First morning void	First morning void	Spot (random)
Serum/plasma/Whole blood											
Serum	√	√	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	√	√	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.
Plasma	√	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	√	√	N.A.	√	√	N.A.
Whole Blood	√	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	√	√	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.

Table 6: Comparison of study characteristics of studies to be aligned targeting teenagers.

Teenagers											
	North		East			South			West		
	NEBII	Riksmaten ungdom 2016-17	POLAES	Pilot study in school children	PCB cohort (follow-up)	SLO CRP	CROME	BEA	ESTEBAN	FLEHS IV	GerES V
<i>Study characteristics</i>											
N	184	300	300	300	300	98	150	300	300	300	300
Age (years)	12-14	12-17	12-14	12-18	15-16	12-15	12-15	14-16	12-19	14-15	12-17
Date range of sample collection	2016	2016-2017	2017	2019	2019	2018	2019	2017-2018	2014-2016	2018	2014-2017
Seasonality											
Spring	√	√	-	-	√	√	-	-	√	√	√
Summer	√	-	-	√	√	√	-	-	√	√	√
Autumn	√	√	√	√	√	-	√	-	√	√	√
winter	√	√	√	-	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Representation	National	National	Regional	Regional	Regional	Regional	Regional	National	National	Regional	National
Study design	Longitudinal	Cross sectional	Case-control	Cross sectional	Longitudinal /cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional
<i>Fieldwork methods / samples collected</i>											
Field blanks collected	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Fasting status	Non-fasting	Non-fasting	-	-	Fasting	Non-fasting	Fasting	Non-fasting	Fasting	Non-fasting	Non-fasting
Type urine sample	First morning void	Spot (random)	Spot (random)	First morning void	First morning void	First morning void	First morning void	Spot (random)	First morning void	Spot (random)	First morning void
Serum/plasma/Whole blood											
Serum	√	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	√	√	√	√	√	N.A.
Plasma	√	√	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	√	√
Whole Blood	√	√	N.A.	N.A.	N.A.	√	√	√	√	√	N.A.

Table 7: Comparison of study characteristics of studies to be aligned targeting adults.

Adults	North			East		South		West			
	CPHMINIPUB (parents)	Diet_HBM	FinHealth	POLAES	ELSPAC	Croatia	INSEF-ExQAP	ESTEBAN	SWISS TPH	ESB	Oriscav Lux 2
<i>Study characteristics</i>											
N	242	200	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	265
Age (years)	25-55	19-39	20-39	20-39	26-28	20-39	28-39	20-39	20-39	20-29	25 -39
Years of sample collection	2018	2019	2017	2017	2019	2019	2019	2014-2016	2019-2020	2014-2019	2016-2017
Seasonality											
Spring	√	-	√	-	√	√	√	√	√	√	√
Summer	√	-	-	-	√	-	-	√	√	-	√
Autumn	√	√	-	√	√	-	-	√	√	-	√
winter	√	√	√	√	-	√	√	√	√	√	√
Representation	Regional	National	National	Regional	Regional	National	National	National	Regional	Regional/local	National
Study design	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Case-control	Longitudinal	Cross sectional	Longitudinal	Cross sectional	Cross sectional	Cross sectional (volunteer)	Cross-sectional
<i>Fieldwork methods / samples collected</i>											
Field blanks collected	Yes	Yes	-	Yes	No	-	Yes	Yes	-	No	-
Fasting status	-	Fasting*	-	-	Fasting	-	-	Fasting	-	Non-fasting	Fasting
Type urine sample	Spot (random)	Spot (random)	Spot (random)	Spot (random)	First morning void	24h pool	Spot (random)				
Serum/plasma/Whole blood											
Serum	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√
Plasma	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	√	√
Whole blood	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	N.A.	√	N.A.	√	√

*Participants are asked to provide a fasting blood sample but non-fasting samples are also accepted.